

Scalarization of vectorial functions

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1 Scalarization

Definition 1. Given $\underline{f} : \mathbb{R} \supseteq D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f} : D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(x) := \int_0^x \left\| \frac{d\underline{f}(u)}{du} \right\| du + \|\underline{f}(0)\|$$

Where $\int_0^x g(u) du$ is the primitive $\bar{G}(x)$ of $g(x)$, with $\bar{G}(0) = 0$.

Theorem 1 (Scalarization of constant). Given $\underline{a} \in \mathbb{R}^n$

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{a} = \|\underline{a}\|$$

Proof.

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{a} = \int_0^x \left\| \frac{d\underline{a}}{du} \right\| du + \|\underline{a}\| = \int_0^x 0 du + \|\underline{a}\| = \|\underline{a}\|$$

□

Remark 1. We will interpret

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(\bar{x}) = [\underline{\psi}(f)](\bar{x})$$

because for Theo. 1

$$\underline{\psi}(f(\bar{x})) = \|f(\bar{x})\|$$

isn't very usefull.

Theorem 2 (Derivate of $\underline{\psi} \underline{f}$).

$$\underline{\psi}' \underline{f} := (\underline{\psi} \underline{f})' = \|\underline{f}'\|$$

Proof.

$$\frac{d\psi f(x)}{dx} = \frac{d \int_0^x \left\| \frac{df(u)}{du} \right\| du}{dx} + \frac{d\|f(0)\|}{dx} \overset{0}{=} \left\| \frac{df(x)}{dx} \right\|$$

□

Theorem 3 (Second derivate of ψf).

$$\psi'' f = \frac{f' \cdot f''}{\|f'\|}$$

Proof. For Theo. 2

$$\frac{d^2\psi f(x)}{dx^2} = \frac{d\|f'(x)\|}{dx} = \frac{f' \cdot f''}{\|f'\|}$$

As the derivate of $\|g(x)\|$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\|g(x)\|}{dx} &= \frac{d\sqrt{\sum g_i(x)^2}}{dx} = \frac{d\sqrt{\sum g_i(x)^2}}{d\sum g_i(x)^2} \frac{d\sum g_i(x)^2}{dx} = \\ &= \frac{d\sqrt{u}}{du} \Big|_{u=\sum g_i(x)^2} \sum \frac{dg_i(x)^2}{dx} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{u}} \Big|_{u=\|g(x)\|^2} \sum \frac{dg_i(x)^2}{dg_i(x)} \frac{dg_i(x)}{dx} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\|g\|} 2 \sum g_i(x)g'_i(x) = \frac{\sum g_i(x)g'_i(x)}{\|g\|} = \frac{g \cdot g'}{\|g\|} \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2 (Second derivate of ψf [TO CHECK]).

$$\psi'' f \propto \|f''\|$$

Proof.

$$\psi'' f = \frac{f' \cdot f''}{\|f'\|} = \frac{\cancel{\|f'\|} \|f''\| \cos(\theta)}{\cancel{\|f'\|}} = \|f''\| \cos(\theta)$$

□

Remark 3 (Derivates of ψf).

$$\psi' f = \|f'\| = \frac{f' \cdot f'}{\|f'\|}$$

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Theorem 4 (Scalarization in zero).

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(0) = \|\underline{f}(0)\|$$

Proof.

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(0) = \int_0^x \left\| \frac{d\underline{f}(u)}{du} \right\| du \Big|_{x=0} + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \overline{G}(0) + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \|\underline{f}(0)\|$$

□

Theorem 5 (Idempotence of $\underline{\psi}$).

$$\underline{\psi} \circ \underline{\psi} = \underline{\psi}$$

Proof.

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{\psi} \underline{f} = \int_0^x \left\| \frac{d\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(u)}{du} \right\| du + \|\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(0)\| =$$

For Theo. 2 and 4

$$= \int_0^x \left\| \left\| \frac{d\underline{f}(u)}{du} \right\| \right\| du + \|\|\underline{f}(0)\|\| = \int_0^x \left\| \frac{d\underline{f}(u)}{du} \right\| du + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \underline{\psi} \underline{f}$$

□

Theorem 6 (Limit by norm). 1. $x > 0$

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(x) \geq \|\underline{f}(x)\| \geq 0$$

2. $x < 0$

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f}(x) \leq \|\underline{f}(x)\|$$

Proof.

$$\underline{\psi} \underline{f} = \int_0^x \|\underline{f}'(u)\| du + \|\underline{f}(0)\| =$$

1. $x > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \left\| \int_0^x \underline{f}'(u) du \right\| + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \left\| \underline{f}(x) \Big|_0^x \right\| + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \\ &= \|\underline{f}(x) - \underline{f}(0)\| + \|\underline{f}(0)\| \geq \|\underline{f}(x) - \underline{f}(0) + \underline{f}(0)\| = \|\underline{f}(x)\| \end{aligned}$$

2. $x < 0$

$$\begin{aligned} &= - \int_x^0 \|\underline{f}'(u)\| du + \|\underline{f}(0)\| \leq - \left\| \int_x^0 \underline{f}'(u) du \right\| + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \\ &= -\|\underline{f}(0) - \underline{f}(x)\| + \|\underline{f}(0)\| \leq \left| \|\underline{f}(0)\| - \|\underline{f}(0) - \underline{f}(x)\| \right| \leq \|\underline{f}(0) - \underline{f}(0) + \underline{f}(x)\| \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 7.

$$\psi \underline{f} = \|\underline{f}\| \iff \exists \alpha : D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \mid \underline{f}'(x) = \alpha(x)\underline{f}(x)$$

Proof.

$$\psi \underline{f} = \|\underline{f}\| \iff \|\underline{f}'\| = \|\underline{f}\|'$$

in fact

$$\psi \underline{f} = \int_0^x \|\underline{f}'\| du + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \int_0^x \|\underline{f}\|' du + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = \|\underline{f}\| - \|\underline{f}(0)\| + \|\underline{f}(0)\|$$

furthermore

$$\|\underline{f}\|' = \frac{\underline{f} \cdot \underline{f}'}{\|\underline{f}\|}$$

and so

$$\begin{aligned} \|\underline{f}\|' = \|\underline{f}'\| &\iff \|\underline{f}\|\|\underline{f}'\| = \underline{f} \cdot \underline{f}' = \|\underline{f}\|\|\underline{f}'\| \cos(\theta) \iff \\ &\iff \cos(\theta) = 1 \iff \theta = 2k\pi; k \in \mathbb{Z} \end{aligned}$$

and $\theta = 2k\pi \iff \underline{f}$ and $\underline{f}'$ have the same direction. □**Theorem 8** (Length of a curve). *Given a curve $\Gamma \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and a parametrization $\underline{\gamma} \in C^1([a, b]) : [a, b] \rightarrow \Gamma$*

$$L(\Gamma) = \psi \underline{\gamma} \Big|_a^b$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \psi \underline{\gamma}(x) &= \int_0^x \|\underline{\gamma}'(t)\| dt + \|\underline{\gamma}(0)\| \\ \psi \underline{\gamma} \Big|_a^b &= \psi \underline{\gamma}(b) - \psi \underline{\gamma}(a) = \int_0^b \|\underline{\gamma}'(t)\| dt - \int_0^a \|\underline{\gamma}'(t)\| dt = \\ &= \int_a^0 \|\underline{\gamma}'(t)\| dt + \int_0^b \|\underline{\gamma}'(t)\| dt = \int_a^b \|\underline{\gamma}'(t)\| dt = \int_{\Gamma} ds = L(\Gamma) \end{aligned}$$

□

Figure 1: $\underline{f}(t) = r (\cos(\omega t), \sin(\omega t))$

2 Examples

Example 1 (Circular motion). Given $r, \omega \in \mathbb{R}^+$

$$\underline{f}(t) = r (\cos(\omega t), \sin(\omega t))$$

visible in Fig. 1

$$\|\underline{f}(0)\| = r$$

$$\dot{\underline{f}} = r\omega (-\sin(\omega t), \cos(\omega t)) \implies \|\dot{\underline{f}}\| = r\omega$$

$$\dot{\underline{w}}f = \int_0^t \|\dot{\underline{f}}\| du + \|\underline{f}(0)\| = r(\omega t + 1)$$

visible in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: $y = \dot{\underline{w}}f$

And, as expected

$$\dot{\underline{w}}f = r\omega = \|\dot{\underline{f}}\|$$